

Teachers' Readiness in the Implementation of Enhanced K-10 Curriculum in Integrated and Private Junior High Schools

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Abstract: This study aimed to examine significant differences in teachers' readiness to implement the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum across Integrated and Private Junior High Schools in the Division of San Carlos City, Negros Occidental. Research measured readiness across six domains: curriculum relevance, impact on learning, pedagogical practices, professional development training, resource availability, and administrative support. A total enumeration survey was conducted among ninety-six (96) identified teachers from eight (8) Integrated and forty-three (43) from five (5) Private Junior High schools during SY 2025–2026. Using a validated Likert-type questionnaire, descriptive statistics were used to describe the variables' levels, and the Chi-Squared test for Homogeneity was used to determine their significant differences. Results showed a significant difference between Integrated and Private Junior High Schools, with p-values of 0.0007 for Administrative Support, 0.0035 for Professional Development Training, and 0.0001 for Resource Availability. This suggests a discrepancy and an insufficiency in the overall Administrative Support Allocation for Integrated Schools compared to Private Schools. Based on these findings, the study proposed an action plan to strengthen curriculum implementation, teacher readiness, and resource management in the Integrated and Private Schools to fully materialize the goals and objectives of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum in the Division of San Carlos City.

Keywords: teacher readiness, Division of San Carlos City Enhanced K-10 curriculum, administrative support, curriculum implementation.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Background of Study

Curriculum reforms are among the most important steps in providing quality education. These reforms reflect priorities, values from different cultures, and ideals for future generations.

Finland requires its teachers to hold a master's degree to fully implement both theoretical and practical approaches in education. Finland believes that this requirement secures high-quality education.

On the other hand, Japan utilizes "lesson study," a collaborative professional development approach in which teachers observe, critique, and provide constructive feedback to one another. This practice allows teachers to share ideas, strategies, and instructional practices that foster professional growth among curriculum implementer.

In Singapore, Jensen (2024) emphasized the importance of structured professional development. This developmental plan is delivered through workshops, mentor-mentee programs, and performance evaluations. This system encourages teachers to continually improve, adapt, and adopt new practices tailored to their professional needs.

In response to global educational developments, the Philippines has adjusted its curriculum to advance its education system and international standing. To remain competitive on a global scale, the Philippines must strengthen its curriculum.

Curriculum advancement must focus on achieving the intended outcomes of education—its primary beneficiaries, the students—and addressing their diverse needs. The Department of Education (2023) stated that the MATATAG Curriculum, as a precursor to the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum, utilizes an abridged lesson design. It emphasizes foundational skills, particularly the 3Rs: reading, writing, and arithmetic.

These foundational skills are integrated with lifelong competencies that are applicable in everyday life. As with any large-scale educational reform, the success of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum heavily depends on the readiness, competence, and adaptability of teachers—the front liners of classroom instruction.

The pursuit of teacher readiness entails not only awareness of new curriculum content but also understanding pedagogical shifts, assessment approaches, and the effective use of technology and contextualized instructional materials (Orbe et al., 2022). Teachers' readiness may also be influenced by inadequate training, mismatched professional development programs, and insufficient instructional resources (Abragan et al., 2022).

This research investigates teachers' readiness to implement the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum, specifically among Junior High School teachers in the Division of San Carlos City. As the implementation of the new curriculum is still in its initial phase, there are limited studies on this topic, particularly within the Division of San Carlos City. Thus, this study seeks to address this gap in the literature.

Beyond examining teachers' readiness, this study also analyzes and compares how secondary-level teachers from Integrated and Private Schools adapt to curricular changes, receive administrative support, and align their instructional strategies with the new standards in implementing the curriculum. Furthermore, this study aims to develop an action plan for the 2026–2027 school year.

Review of Related Literature

Inconsistent and unsustainable training and professional development significantly hinder the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Many educators have called for more comprehensive and sustainable capacity-building programs to address emerging educational demands (Sarmiento & Tablatin, 2021). Without continuous support and opportunities for skill enhancement, teachers' ability to deliver high-quality and effective instruction is compromised.

Further research has underscored major challenges in curriculum implementation, particularly in terms of teacher preparedness and inclusive education. Andrin's study (2024) found that teachers

in urban areas demonstrated more optimistic perceptions of curriculum implementation than those in rural areas, highlighting disparities in access to resources and training. Similarly, a study conducted in Cavite revealed that teachers felt less prepared to implement the new curriculum due to inadequate training and limited capacity to manage large class sizes (Bayot, 2025).

A parallel study in the Division of Iloilo City assessed 421 teachers during the 2024–2025 school year. The study examined teacher readiness, professional development needs, and challenges encountered in implementing the MATATAG Curriculum. Although teachers acknowledged the curriculum's potential to improve student achievement, concerns were raised regarding insufficient training and the scarcity of instructional resources (Elardo, 2025).

In Calabarzon, Gutierrez (as cited in DepEd studies on teacher preparedness) deduced that teachers had limited experience in delivering basic food and nutrition lessons, conducting experiments related to nutritional status, and facilitating food laboratory activities. Effective instruction in these areas requires teachers to competently manage hands-on activities and accurately interpret food and nutrition data. Gutierrez's findings further supported the Department of Education's observations regarding teachers' preparedness for MATATAG Curriculum implementation, emphasizing the complexity of teachers' roles and the difficulties they encounter when adjusting to educational reforms.

Addressing inequalities and mismatches in training and resource allocation is a critical step toward ensuring that all teachers can implement the curriculum effectively and efficiently. Teachers' perceptions of the new curriculum—including their views of its relevance and value—play a vital role in how they adjust their instructional approaches. Collaborative programs established with universities or industry partners, such as those in the food sector, may help teachers attain the competencies required by the curriculum. MATATAG Curriculum as the Relevant Basis of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

A positive mindset among teachers facilitates the necessary adjustments for successful curriculum adoption, motivating educators to embrace new approaches and content aligned with reforms. Instructional flexibility is essential, as it directly affects the quality of teaching and learning and ultimately influences student achievement. Therefore, ongoing and sustainable professional development, along with strong administrative support, is crucial in fostering positive teacher perceptions and ensuring effective curriculum implementation.

The Philippine education system has long faced issues of curriculum overload. Pillay and Panth (2022) noted that teachers experience significant pressure in addressing numerous competencies within limited instructional time. In response to persistent concerns regarding curriculum congestion, low student performance, and teacher strain, the MATATAG Curriculum prioritizes foundational skills, values education, and a streamlined content load to support more focused learning and holistic development.

The Enhanced K–10 Curriculum reflects these reforms. Its primary goal is to simplify lessons, emphasize reading, mathematics, and practical skills, and enhance the relevance of learning to real-life contexts (Department of Education, 2023). Dayola et al. (2024) observed that educators commended the curriculum's efficient design, which enables more focused and effective instructional delivery.

Moreover, Prado and Asparin (2025) found that learners reported reduced stress levels and increased engagement in discussions through hands-on learning activities. Their study also revealed that educators generally held favorable views of the MATATAG Curriculum, particularly regarding its relevance and alignment with essential educational competencies.

In contrast, Tarraya (2023) identified persistent challenges, including crowded competencies and high teaching expectations, which contributed to academic burden and teacher burnout. These

concerns highlighted the need for comprehensive policy responses, including increased government resource allocation and improved access to quality education, given education's critical role in national economic sustainability.

Using the PRISMA framework, Cabaya et al. (2025) reviewed 25 studies published between 2020 and 2025. The selected studies were analyzed thematically, and a notable reduction in learning competencies emerged as a key structural reform. The issue of K–12 content congestion was directly addressed, promoting deeper exploration, practical application, and mastery rather than superficial coverage of topics.

Given these contrasting findings, the present study seeks to examine which perspectives are reflected in the local context and how they relate to teachers' readiness in implementing the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

On Teachers' Readiness

Unsustainable training and professional development greatly hinder the effectiveness of teaching and learning. However, many educators have called for more comprehensive and sustainable capacity-building programs to address emerging educational demands (Sarmiento & Tablatin, 2021). Without continuous support and opportunities for skill enhancement, teachers' ability to deliver high-quality and effective instruction is significantly compromised.

Further research has underscored major difficulties in curriculum implementation, particularly in terms of teacher preparedness and inclusive education. Andrin (2024) found that teachers in urban areas had more optimistic perceptions than those in rural areas, highlighting disparities in access to resources and training. In Cavite, a study revealed that teachers felt less prepared to implement the new curriculum due to inadequate training and limited capacity to manage large class sizes (Bayot, 2025). A parallel study was conducted in the Division of Iloilo City, where 421 teachers were assessed during the 2024–2025 school year. The study examined teacher readiness, professional needs, and the challenges encountered in implementing the MATATAG curriculum.

Although teachers acknowledged the curriculum's potential to improve student achievement, concerns were raised regarding inadequate training and the scarcity of instructional resources (Elardo, 2025). In CALABARZON, Gutierrez (2025) also found that teachers had limited experience in basic food lessons, nutritional assessment, and food laboratory skills. To effectively teach these subjects, teachers must be able to facilitate hands-on activities and interpret food and nutrition data. Gutierrez's study further supported the findings of the Department of Education (DepEd) regarding teachers' preparedness for MATATAG curriculum implementation, emphasizing the complexity of teachers' roles and the challenges they encounter when adapting to educational reforms.

Addressing inequalities and mismatches is a crucial first step in ensuring that all teachers can implement the curriculum effectively and efficiently. Teachers' perceptions of the new curriculum, including their views of its value, play a vital role in their adjustment to changes in instructional approaches. Programs established in collaboration with universities or food industries may help teachers attain the competencies required by the curriculum.

The MATATAG Curriculum serves as a relevant basis for the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. A positive mindset encourages necessary adjustments for successful adoption, motivating educators to embrace new approaches and content aligned with educational reforms. Instructional flexibility is essential, as it influences the quality of teaching and learning and ultimately affects learners' achievement. Thus, ongoing and sustainable professional development, along with strong administrative support, is crucial in fostering positive teacher perceptions and ensuring successful curriculum implementation.

The Philippine education system has long faced curriculum overload. Pillay and Panth (2022) noted that teachers in the country experience significant pressure to address numerous competencies within a limited time frame. To address persistent issues such as curriculum overload, inadequate student performance, and teacher strain, the MATATAG curriculum prioritizes foundational skills, values education, and a streamlined content load to support more focused learning and development. The Enhanced K–10 Curriculum reflects these changes, aiming to simplify lessons, strengthen reading, mathematics, and practical skills, and enhance the relevance of learning to real-life contexts (Department of Education, 2023).

Dayola et al. (2024) likewise reported that educators commend the curriculum's efficient design, which enables more focused and effective instructional delivery. Similarly, Prado and Asparin (2025) found that learners experienced reduced stress and greater engagement through hands-on learning activities. Their study also indicated that educators' perceptions of the MATATAG curriculum were largely favorable, particularly regarding its relevance and alignment with educational competencies.

In contrast, Tarraya (2023) identified several challenges in the curriculum, including congested competencies and high teaching expectations, which contribute to academic burden and teacher burnout. These concerns highlight the need for a comprehensive response, including increased government resource allocation and improved access to quality education, as education remains a sustaining force in the country's economic development.

Using the PRISMA framework, Cabaya et al. (2025) reviewed 25 recent studies published between 2020 and 2025. The studies were analyzed thematically, and a notable decrease in learning competencies emerged as a key structural reform. The issue of K–12 content congestion was directly addressed, promoting deeper exploration, application, and mastery rather than superficial coverage.

Based on these differing perspectives, the present study seeks to determine which conceptual stance it aligns with.

On Administrative Support and Resource Availability

Conducive environments, as emphasized in the Theory of Self-Efficacy, promote teamwork, collaboration, and creativity. These factors enable teachers to address curriculum reforms, academic stress, and burnout effectively. Alongside individual teacher preparedness, establishing a strong support system is crucial to the successful implementation of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. Roos and Borkoski (2021) highlighted the importance of fostering healthy and supportive school environments, which often prioritize teacher well-being and sustainable professional development.

Similarly, a study conducted in South Africa found that teachers struggled with curricular changes due to inadequate and inaccessible resources (Soudien, 2020). Comparable findings were reported in a descriptive study by Demate et al. (2025), which examined the perspectives of seven (7) Grades 1 to 4 teachers from randomly selected schools in Cebu City, Philippines. In research on the MATATAG Curriculum, dissatisfaction was expressed regarding insufficient systemic support. It was also noted that the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum progressed rapidly. The study concluded that a comprehensive and responsive support system is necessary to address professional development needs and ensure equitable access to learning resources. These findings align with Lopez's (2022) research, which emphasized that many educators continue to face limited access to resources, brief training sessions, and inadequate assistance in subject alignment. These factors greatly hinder teachers' ability to implement new teaching strategies effectively and efficiently.

In terms of administrative responsiveness, challenges such as high student–teacher ratios and classroom shortages are further exacerbated by insufficient support for contextualized learning materials (Llego, 2020).

Due to its sudden implementation, the MATATAG Curriculum encountered significant challenges and criticism. Javier (2023) identified several issues, including the need for effective implementation strategies, inadequate government policies supporting inclusive education, and practical difficulties during curriculum roll out. Access to adequate resources, collaborative planning, and regular training sessions were deemed essential to effective teaching and learning. Extensive state support, including sustained professional development and equitable resource allocation, has been associated with progressive outcomes (Abragan et al., 2022).

Similarly, Magsambol (2024) underscored the importance of administrative support in the effective implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum. The study found that teachers who received equitable support and sufficient resources from school administrations reported more positive experiences and higher levels of student engagement. The research also emphasized the need for stronger collaboration among teachers and stakeholders to identify concerns and address them through practical and cost-efficient solutions (Magsambol, 2024).

On Professional Development

Although the MATATAG Curriculum envisions a major reform goal, Lastimosa and Dagondon (2025) emphasized that its successful implementation depends heavily on systemic institutional support and teacher readiness. The study found that professional development and effective curriculum implementation are critical in translating policy objectives into classroom-based learning. In addition, the shortage of trained teachers poses a significant obstacle to the program’s successful implementation, resulting in inconsistent educational experiences across schools.

Deficient teacher training and limited professional development opportunities have been identified as significant factors contributing to challenges in educational delivery (Quijano, 2023). Teachers have also reported that participation in only one formal training session—particularly among newly hired teachers—was common prior to the implementation of the MATATAG Curriculum. Since then, no supplementary training sessions or follow-up programs have been conducted, which has adversely affected ongoing preparedness and teachers’ ability to deliver the curriculum effectively.

Synthesis

In addressing issues of curriculum overload and poor curricular outcomes, the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum has become a central focus. Numerous studies in the literature show that by streamlining content, emphasizing foundational and lifelong skills, and ensuring the curriculum’s relevance in both local and global contexts, the newly established curriculum offers a progressive approach. However, the literature presents conflicting views on whether the MATATAG Curriculum serves as a precursor to the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. Although many teachers commend the curriculum’s simplified structure and its potential to enhance instructional focus, others raise concerns about increased academic workload.

Multiple studies also indicate that teachers feel unprepared to implement the curriculum due to inadequate resources, unsustainable professional training, and inaccessible learning materials. These constraints compromise the delivery of quality education and hinder the instructional adaptability required of teachers.

On the other hand, a robust support structure—including strong administrative support, collaborative planning within the educational system, and attention to appropriate student–teacher ratios—is essential for effective curriculum implementation. Lastly, teacher well-being and self-

efficacy must be actively supported to reduce resistance and transform the curriculum from a policy initiative into a genuinely substantive tool for student learning.

Theoretical Framework

Self-efficacy, a concept introduced by psychologist Albert Bandura (1977), refers to an individual's confidence in their ability to execute behaviors required to achieve specific performance outcomes. It also pertains to one's perceived capacity to influence situations and regulate one's environment. Self-efficacy is not merely a measure of aptitude; rather, it reflects an individual's judgment of what they can accomplish using the skills, knowledge, and resources they possess.

For teachers implementing the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum, those with higher self-efficacy are more likely to demonstrate readiness, set ambitious yet realistic goals aligned with the new curriculum, persist through challenges, and overcome obstacles efficiently. Self-efficacy serves as a strong indicator of a teacher's willingness to adapt instructional practices and implement the student-centered and activity-based approaches advocated by the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

Conversely, low self-efficacy may result in the avoidance of complex tasks, such as facilitating hands-on activities or integrating technology into instruction. Teachers who firmly believe they are prepared to implement the new curriculum are more likely to do so effectively and confidently. They are also more inclined to foster a conducive, collaborative, open, and positive learning environment. In turn, this contributes to increased student engagement and improved academic achievement.

Over time, this creates a cumulative effect: high teacher self-efficacy promotes successful instructional practices, and successful experiences further strengthen efficacy beliefs. Ultimately, this not only enhances the effectiveness of the teaching process but also exerts a substantial positive impact on student learning outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

As shown in Figure 1 on page 6, the conceptual framework of this study focused on the significant differences in teachers' readiness between Integrated and Private Junior High Schools in implementing the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

The independent variable was the type of school, specifically Integrated and Private Secondary Schools. The indicators associated with this variable included: (a) Administrative Support; (b) Impact on Learning; (c) Pedagogical Practices; (d) Professional Development Training; (e) Relevance of the Curriculum; and (f) Resource Availability.

Meanwhile, the dependent variable was the level of agreement among teachers regarding their readiness, defined as their self-efficacy in delivering the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. The results of the dependent variable were based on the data and responses gathered in relation to the independent variables. This relationship was assessed through data collection, statistical analysis, and hypothesis testing.

The framework illustrated how these factors explained the relationship between the independent and dependent variables and clarified why and how the level of teacher readiness differed across types of institutions.

Furthermore, the framework emphasized the importance of analyzing respondents' responses. The analysis served as the foundation for generating new knowledge, recommending development programs for the department and the Division of San Carlos City, and providing a basis for future studies.

Statement of the Problem

This study sought to determine whether there is a significant difference in teachers' readiness to implement the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum during the 2025-2026 school year between Integrated and Private High Schools in the Division of San Carlos City. Specifically, it aims to answer:

1. What is the level of agreement in terms of readiness of the teachers from Junior High School of Integrated and Private Schools towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum as indicated by:
 - a. Impact on learning;
 - b. Pedagogical Practices; and
 - c. Relevance of the curriculum?
2. What is the level of agreement in terms of readiness of the teachers from Junior High School of Integrated and Private Schools towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum, as indicated by:
 - a. Administrative Support;
 - b. Professional Development and Training; and
 - c. Resource Availability?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of agreement in terms of readiness between Integrated and Private Schools teachers in the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum?
4. What developmental plans may be formulated based on the findings?

Hypothesis

H_a : There is a significant difference in the readiness of teachers from Junior High Schools of Public-Integrated and Private Schools in the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum.

Significance of the study

Department of Education. The study provided data highlighting systemic differences between the public and private sectors. Data derived from this study are useful, as they can serve as a basis for future policies. Given that Integrated Schools often face unequal resources and constraints on administrative support, they may receive targeted support to bridge gaps and strengthen teacher readiness as the new curriculum is implemented.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Conceptual Framework

Schools Division Superintendents. Administrators from Public and Private schools gained insights and evaluated teachers' readiness under their care. Data derived from indicators can be used to develop differentiated support systems that are responsive to schools' needs, thereby improving the efficiency of implementing the new curriculum.

School Heads. This study can be used to validate resource shortages that need immediate administrative support. For Private schools, the data from this study is beneficial, as it can be used to benchmark the school's readiness against public schools. This ensures educational input that maximizes outcomes in delivering the curriculum.

Teachers. This study can serve as the foundation for gaining insights and provide clearer understanding, not only of the strengths and weaknesses, but also of the expected competencies for the curriculum implementation, enabling teachers to identify their specific areas for professional development.

Parents. Understanding the challenges teachers face in terms of readiness helps parents become more effective advocates for necessary school improvements and provide relevant support for their children at home, especially in areas where schools are struggling.

Future researchers. This study can serve as a basis for further research on this topic and provide a crucial baseline measure during the initial stages of Enhanced K-10 Curriculum implementation, serving as a point of comparison for future longitudinal or follow-up studies.

Scope of the Study

The objective of this study was to assess the level of agreement among teachers regarding their readiness to implement the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum in the Division of San Carlos City. Quantitative in nature, teachers' readiness was measured using a 4-point Likert scale across various indicators. As this was the first year of curriculum implementation, the study focused on teachers handling Grades 7 and 8 in Integrated and Private Schools. The data were collected during the Academic Year 2025–2026. Total enumeration was employed to determine the number of participants.

In the field of education, this study produced findings specifically on the level of readiness among teachers in Integrated and Private Schools for the implementation of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

Definition of Terms

In this study, the terms used as parameters were operationally defined as follows:

Administrative Support. In this study, this term was defined as a set of systematic and coordinated procedures in human resource management. This included teacher training, instructional support mechanisms, and resource allocation to enable teachers to effectively deliver the curriculum.

Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. In this study, the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum referred to the specific instructional guide, learning standards, competencies, and required teaching methodologies prescribed by official DepEd issuances, including Curriculum Guides and policy memoranda in effect at the time of data collection, intended for implementation at the Junior High School level (Grades 7–10).

Implementation. In this study, this term was viewed as the teachers' reported adoption of the new curriculum's required pedagogical shifts, such as reduced content focus and increased emphasis on foundational skills (literacy and numeracy) and 21st-century skills (critical thinking, purposive communication, collaboration, and lifelong skills), as indicated by specific items in the readiness survey.

Curriculum Relevance. In this study, curriculum relevance was defined as the focus on core competencies, essential content, and foundational skills aligned with learners' developmental levels. It was also viewed as the curriculum's capacity to integrate learners' diverse abilities and learning needs.

Impact on Learning. In this study, this term was defined as the effect of curriculum reforms in the Philippines on learners' achievement, curricular outcomes, teachers' workload, and access to quality education. It was measured by the curriculum's ability to reduce content overload and redundancy and to strengthen foundational skills.

Pedagogical Practices. In this study, pedagogical practices were defined as the methods, strategies, and approaches used by teachers in Integrated and Private Schools to deliver and facilitate learning, shaped by curriculum goals, learners' needs, and the local context.

Professional Development Trainings. In this study, this term was defined as continuous in-service training initiatives that provided teachers with updated strategies, practices, and methodologies to improve curriculum implementation. These programs ensured that teachers were able to adapt to curricular changes.

Resource Availability. In this study, resource availability was defined as the extent to which schools, teachers, and learners had equitable access to sufficient instructional materials, classrooms, facilities, learning equipment, and financial support necessary for curriculum implementation. The study also examined how resource availability affected curriculum outcomes.

Teacher Readiness. In this study, teacher readiness was measured using a composite score derived from a teacher-readiness survey. The instrument assessed familiarity with curricular principles and components, competence in applying new pedagogical approaches, perceived self-efficacy, and willingness to adapt to the new curriculum.

Chapter 2

METHODOLOGY

This chapter compiled the methods and approaches used in the study, including the research design, population, research instrument, data collection procedures, statistical treatment, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

The researcher used a descriptive-comparative research design for this study. Quantitative in nature, this approach was suitable for examining relationships between independent and dependent variables. Quantitative research involves the collection and analysis of numerical data to identify relationships, patterns, or differences (Creswell & Creswell, 2020). It provided insights into the research data, leading to recommendations relevant to the field and area of study.

Using a descriptive-comparative design, the study identified and analyzed variations in specific variables across distinct groups. This process involved describing existing conditions and comparing them to draw meaningful inferences without manipulating independent variables (Fraenkel et al., 2019). The study examined perceived differences between Public and Private School teachers in the implementation of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum.

In descriptive-comparative research, the primary objective is to determine whether a significant difference exists between naturally occurring groups. In this study, the researcher determined whether there was a significant difference in teacher readiness scores between Integrated and Private Junior High School teachers. Specifically, the design enabled the researcher to examine whether the type of school to which a teacher belonged affected the level of teacher readiness, as reflected in parameters such as teachers’ attitudes, perceived impact of the curriculum, pedagogical practices, professional training received, availability of resources, and administrative support.

The use of this method provided empirical evidence to inform administrators, policymakers, teachers, and professional development programs aimed at improving teacher readiness, school preparedness, and curriculum implementation outcomes.

Respondents of the Study

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

RESPONDENTS	n	%
Integrated Schools		
SCHOOL A	6	6.25
SCHOOL B	6	6.25
SCHOOL C	7	7.29
SCHOOL D	6	6.25
SCHOOL E	7	7.29

SCHOOL F	8	8.33
SCHOOL G	6	6.25
SCHOOL H	7	7.29
	53	55.21
Private Schools		
SCHOOL I	9	9.38
SCHOOL J	9	9.38
SCHOOL K	8	8.33
SCHOOL L	8	8.33
SCHOOL M	9	9.38
TOTAL	43	44.79
TOTAL (INTEGRATED + PRIVATE SCHOOLS)	96	100

Table 1 above presents the respondents of the study. This study focused on Grade 7 and Grade 8 teachers from both Public and Private Schools within the Division of San Carlos City. A total of 53 teachers were drawn from one coded Integrated School, and 43 teachers were drawn from five coded Private Schools, resulting in 96 respondents in the study. The sampling technique employed was total enumeration, which involved including the entire population of interest as respondents (Lærd Dissertation, 2020).

The participating institutions included eight (8) Integrated Schools and five (5) Private Schools. Only Grade 7 and Grade 8 teachers were selected as respondents because the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum was in its first year of implementation, making it an appropriate period to evaluate curriculum implementation.

Data Collection Procedure

Prior to conducting the study, a letter of permission was secured from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of San Carlos City to obtain approval before distributing the research instrument to various Integrated and Private Schools within the division.

Upon approval, the researcher conducted a courtesy call with the school head where the study was to be conducted, followed by the voluntary participation of respondents through informed consent. The actual data collection process then commenced with the identified respondents. In cases of technical or travel-related constraints encountered by the researcher, a Google Form was utilized for schools located in remote areas.

After collecting the completed questionnaires from the respondents, the researcher tallied and coded the responses. The gathered data were then processed for analysis and interpretation. Statistical computations were performed using appropriate statistical software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed in accordance with the objectives stated in the study.

Research Instrument

A questionnaire was the primary research instrument used in this study. According to Willis (2020), a questionnaire is “a data collection instrument consisting of a series of questions designed to collect data from respondents in a systematic manner.” It is one of the most widely used techniques in descriptive and survey research because it enables researchers to collect large amounts of data from a specific group efficiently.

The questionnaire developed for this study consisted of three components: (1) a set of Likert-scale items measuring the level of teachers’ agreement regarding the implementation of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum; (2) Likert-scale items measuring the level of administrative support received by teachers; and (3) items gathering respondents’ demographic profile. Respondents were asked to

indicate the response that best suited them and to rate their agreement with each statement on a four-point scale ranging from “Strongly Disagree” (1) to “Strongly Agree” (4).

Questionnaires may be viewed as an interaction between the researcher and the respondent, in which knowledge is not merely collected but shaped through a structured form of communication (Ranganathan & Caduff, 2023). The questionnaire was considered appropriate for this study because it supported the study’s comparative design, enhanced the reliability of the instrument, and facilitated a comprehensive examination of the relationships between the independent and dependent variables.

Validity of the Instrument

According to Golafshani (2023), validity refers to the degree to which a measuring instrument achieves its intended purpose—specifically, whether it measures what it is designed to measure. Each item in the survey questionnaire underwent content validation by four experts, who evaluated the instrument using the criteria developed by Good and Scates. The experts provided ratings for each item, which were subsequently averaged to obtain a scale-level mean validity score.

The instrument yielded an overall mean validity score of 4.11, which was interpreted as “Excellent.”

Reliability of the Instrument

Sürücü and Maslakçı (2020) explained that to ensure a research instrument produces stable and reliable results, conducting a reliability test is essential. In simple terms, research reliability refers to the ability of an instrument to yield consistent results when administered repeatedly and across different cases.

Using Cronbach’s alpha (α) to assess the internal consistency of the 30-item scale across different indicators, the instrument yielded an alpha coefficient of 0.851. This result indicated acceptable internal consistency. A reliability coefficient of 0.70 or higher is widely accepted for broad-level studies in educational settings, thereby supporting the reliability and consistency of the indicator scores in this study.

Data Analysis Procedure

In this study, appropriate statistical treatments were applied, including frequency and percentage distributions for demographic data and weighted means to determine the level of agreement among teachers regarding readiness.

To address the research questions, various data analysis techniques were employed. For Research Questions 1 and 2, descriptive statistics—specifically frequency, percentage, and weighted mean—were used. Descriptive methods were utilized to describe and compare the characteristics of the two groups (Integrated and Private Junior High Schools).

For Research Question 3, inferential statistics were applied. The Chi-Square Test for Homogeneity was used to test the hypothesis concerning differences between the groups. This test enabled the researcher to determine whether a statistically significant difference existed between Integrated and Private Junior High Schools in terms of teacher readiness.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical treatments were used in processing the data collected from the survey.

To answer Research Question 1, which concerned the level of agreement regarding readiness between Integrated and Private Junior High School teachers—as indicated by impact on learning, pedagogical practices, and curriculum relevance—the weighted mean was utilized.

$$WX̄ = \frac{(S1 (W5) + S2 (W4) + S3 (W3) + S4 (W2) + S5 (W1))}{N}$$

Where:

S=responses

N= number of cases

W= weight assigned to the scale

WX̄= weighted mean

To interpret the weighted mean values, the following arbitrary tables were used as references.

Scale of Interpretation	Mean Range	Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree (A)
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree (D)
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree (SDA)

To answer question 2, which concerns the level of agreement in readiness between Integrated and Private Junior High school teachers, as indicated by administrative support, professional development training, and resource availability, the weighted means are also used, using the same reference as in question 1.

To answer question 3, which aimed to identify differences and evaluate significant differences between Integrated and Private High School teachers, the Chi-Squared test of Homogeneity was used. As a statistical tool, this will determine whether the two populations (Integrated and Private Schools) have the same level of agreement regarding readiness.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Formula Components:

χ^2 : Chi-Square statistic.

\sum : Summation symbol (sum of all categories/cells).

O_i : Observed frequency (actual value).

E_i : Expected frequency (theoretical value).

To test the hypothesis:

(df): degrees of freedom

p-value: $p > \alpha$ ($p > 0.05$): Failed to reject H_0

p-value: $p \leq \alpha$: reject H_0

Ethical Considerations

This research was presented to the Graduate School of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos, Inc. as part of the institution's academic requirements. To uphold transparency, credibility, and compliance with ethical research standards, strict protocols were consistently followed during the data collection phase.

To protect the participants and uphold ethical standards throughout the research process, informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to the commencement of any research activities.

Letters of permission from the concerned administrators were also secured. It was clearly explained that all data collected from participants would be kept confidential and that no names would be used, in whole or in part, in any section of the study.

Chapter 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter documented the data gathered, its analysis, and the interpretation of findings derived from the study's respondents. It also presented the study's responses to the research problems and hypotheses.

The study analyzed teachers' level of agreement regarding their readiness to implement the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum across Junior High Schools in Integrated and Private Schools. It summarized teachers' perceptions of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. In terms of curriculum implementation as shown in Table 1 on page 30, the indicators measured teachers' levels of agreement concerning their readiness, including the curriculum's impact on learning, teachers' pedagogical practices, and the relevance of the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. On the other hand, to measure the level of agreement regarding the support received by teachers, several variables were utilized, including administrative support, professional development training, and resource availability.

In total, 96 respondents participated in the study, representing multiple schools and providing a balanced perspective of both the Integrated and Private School contexts.

On the other hand, Critical Thinking and Communication skills were reflected by 62.50% ($f=60$). The results indicated that teachers' beliefs confirm that the curriculum targets and aids the development of higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), while emphasizing the importance of lower-order thinking skills (LOTS). The alignment ultimately increased the likelihood that students can personalize and apply these skills rather than memorize them. This also served as a basis for mandating assessment tools that captured rubrics for reasoning, critical thinking, and communication. This also paves the way to move beyond paper-and-pencil assessments by including analytic scoring guidelines.

Table 2. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum in terms of Impact on Learning

A. IMPACT ON LEARNING Indicators	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL		
The curriculum encourages experimenting, discovery learning, and hands-on activities.	41	25	66	10	17	27	2	1	3	0	0	0	3.66	SA
Critical thinking, problem-solving, and purposive communication skills are tailored in the curriculum.	32	28	60	21	15	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.63	SA
The Revised K-10 Curriculum prioritizes strengthening foundational skills such as numeracy and literacy.	37	26	63	14	12	26	2	5	7	0	0	0	3.58	SA
Real-world scenarios and challenges are emphasized in the curriculum.	33	23	56	17	20	37	1	0	1	0	0	0	3.51	SA
Diversity of learners is accommodated in the curriculum.	33	20	53	15	15	30	5	8	13	0	0	0	3.42	SA
													3.56	SA

Overall, the respondents reported a weighted mean of 3.56 (Strongly Agree), indicating that, in this area, teachers believe the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum has a significant impact on students and teachers alike. These findings support the MATATAG Curriculum's stated goal of addressing learning poverty and strengthening foundational skills (DepEd, 2026; World Bank, 2021).

Table 3. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum in terms of Pedagogical Practices

PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES Indicators	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL	IS f	PS f	TOTAL		
Creates connections between my lessons and real-life scenarios.	42	36	78	10	7	17	1	0	1	0	0	0	3.80	SA
Employed a student-centered approach to promote active learning inside the classroom.	38	34	72	15	9	24	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.75	SA
Develops lesson plans that are aligned to the objectives and competencies of the curriculum.	38	33	71	15	10	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	3.74	SA
Follows the curriculum's content, sequence, and assessment requirements.	39	30	69	13	13	26	1	0	1	0	0	0	3.71	SA
Utilizes differentiated instructions to cater to learners' diverse needs.	40	26	66	12	17	29	1	0	1	0	0	0	3.68	SA
													3.74	SA

In Table 3, the pedagogical readiness was the strongest area. Teachers who connect lessons to real-life scenarios received the highest endorsement, with a weighted mean of 3.80 ($f=78$; strongly agree). This implies that teachers strongly believe the curriculum should and does situate learning in authentic contexts, community problems, workplace simulations, and everyday applications, making transfer of knowledge explicit, holistic, life-long, and meaningful (OECD, 2021; World Bank, 2022). In addition, a student-centered approach was affirmed by 75% ($f=72$) of the total population, who responded strongly agree. A large majority of teachers strongly endorse shifting classroom practice toward learner-centered pedagogy, less teacher talk, more student engagement, active learning, and formative interaction. This signaled teachers' readiness to adopt practices that increase engagement and deeper learning.

Differentiated instruction was supported by a weighted mean of 3.68 ($f=66$) of respondents who strongly agreed. The result clearly indicates that teachers endorse differentiated teaching strategies that adapt content and needs, but a substantial share only "agree," suggesting varying confidence among teachers. Additionally, the result is congruent with the Differentiation and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) approaches, which emphasize targeted support for diverse learners (UNICEF & UNESCO, 2021; Gove & Wetterberg, 2020).

Based on all indicators, the weighted mean was 3.74, indicating strong agreement on pedagogical approaches. These data highlighted that teachers are not merely at the conceptual level but also, in an adaptive sense, employ learner-focused teaching strategies. This level of agreement is also indicated in the study of Abaiz et al. (2025). In the study, teachers embraced advanced strategies but needed clearer guidelines and materials. These included student-centered approaches, contextually relevant objectives, and alignment with existing global standards.

Table 4. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum in terms of the Relevance of the Curriculum

C. RELEVANCE OF CURRICULUM	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL		
Indicators	f	f		f	f		f	f		f	f			
Essential skills and competencies are embodied in the Curriculum.	36	24	60	17	18	35	0	1	1	0	0	0	3.61	SA
Objectives are well-defined and age-appropriate.	35	14	49	15	24	39	3	5	8	0	0	0	3.43	SA
Curriculum is relevant to the needs in local settings	25	22	47	24	16	40	4	5	9	0	0	0	3.40	SA
Essential skills and competencies are aligned with global needs.	25	17	42	24	20	44	4	6	10	0	0	0	3.33	SA
The curriculum's contents are well organized and non-redundant.	24	11	35	17	20	37	12	12	24	0	0	0	3.11	A
													3.38	SA

Based on the data in Table 4, most respondents affirmed the curriculum's relevance, producing a weighted mean of 3.61 (Strongly Agreed). These data indicate that foundational skills and learning competencies are present across all items, suggesting that teachers perceived the Enhanced K-10 curriculum as practical and meaningful. The high proportion also showed that most teachers believed the curriculum was clearly aligned with the needs of society and the field of work. In practice, this level of agreement suggests that teachers are likely to accept and implement curriculum changes, invest in lesson plans aligned with students' needs, and communicate with parents with confidence.

On the other hand, the organization of the curriculum was less consistent, with a weighted mean of 3.11 (f=35), indicating strong agreement. Teachers endorsed the organization fully, as reflected in the data, with only minor concerns. However, these "small" concerns may pose a risk. Redundant or unclear competencies may increase planning time, confuse assessment, and diminish instructional focus, especially for core competencies. In these terms, redundancy and misalignment among the prioritized competencies may also affect the Enhanced K-10 curriculum's alignment with global standards, thereby undermining the learners' competitiveness globally.

Taken as a whole, respondents produced a weighted mean of 3.38 (Strongly Agree) as an aggregate score. This implied that the Enhanced K-10 curriculum allowed student learning by prioritizing foundational skills and core competencies. This indicator captured teachers' level of agreement on whether the Enhanced K-10 curriculum embodied basic skills, was age-appropriate, organized competencies effectively, and aligned with global standards.

In the Philippine context, policies were analyzed to determine whether the Enhanced K-10 curriculum aligned with the said standards. This perception was important because teachers' belief in curricular relevance is a primary factor in curriculum reforms and their implementation.

Table 5. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum in terms of the Administrative Support

ADMINISTRATIVE SUPPORT	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL		
Indicators	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f		
The education system conducts continuous curriculum implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.	36	20	56	17	22	39	0	1	1	0	0	0	3.57	SA
School heads provide sufficient support to the teachers during the implementation.	29	22	51	16	17	33	8	3	11	0	1	1	3.40	SA
Policies and guidelines communicated by school administrators for implementing the Revised K-10 Curriculum are consistent and unambiguous.	22	15	37	17	22	39	14	6	20	0	0	0	3.18	A
Training is provided in the implementation of the Revised K-10 Curriculum	19	23	42	16	15	31	14	5	19	4	0	4	3.16	A
The system addresses teachers' concerns about curriculum implementation.	17	16	33	12	19	31	15	7	22	9	1	10	2.91	A
													3.24	A

In Table 5, monitoring and evaluation were affirmed by a weighted mean of 3.57 ($f=51$), indicating strong agreement. This outlined the majority's perception that monitoring and evaluation are present and visible throughout the schools (DepEd, 2022). This also highlighted a clear pattern: teachers perceive an open feedback mechanism and follow-up evaluation processes (Navarro, Bonganciso, & Gadian, 2023). However, the system is characterized by repeated questions about the effectiveness of mechanisms. Monitoring is formative, although it may include assistance with instructions, practical feedback, and constructive criticisms. Nevertheless, this does not mean that the presence of such indicators guarantees quality and effectiveness; they can be present solely for compliance. These arguments reflect that presence does not mean better quality. Lastly, Philippine education reforms showed that Monitoring and Evaluation processes may vary among schools, depending on the school's area and systemic support.

However, responsiveness to teacher concerns was weaker, with a mean of only 2.91 ($f=33$), indicating strong agreement. The data showed an average level of overall certainty regarding administrative responsiveness, with a considerable number of minorities reporting that teachers' concerns about curriculum implementation were not heard or addressed properly. Teachers also believed that mechanisms for receiving and responding to teacher feedback are in place, but the level of discontent with this indicator is operationally significant. With an output of 3.24 (Agree) as the general weighted mean, administrative leadership and monitoring are comparative strengths that support the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum, implying strong monitoring presence, but uneven access to follow-ups (EDCOM II; OECD, 2023).

Table 6. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum in terms of the Professional Development

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT TRAINING Indicators	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL		
	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f		
The training I received allowed me to be adequately ready for the implementation of the Revised K-10 curriculum	40	20	60	9	17	26	4	6	10	0	0	0	3.52	SA
The school ensures ongoing feedback through Focus Group Discussions and the School Learning Action Cell to address concerns and collaborate on improvements.	35	23	58	13	15	28	5	5	10	0	0	0	3.50	SA
Necessary professional development sessions and seminars are delivered on the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum	35	21	56	13	17	30	5	5	10	0	0	0	3.48	SA
The training included theoretical and practical strategies.	30	19	49	20	21	41	3	2	5	0	1	1	3.44	SA
The training and seminars I attended were applied to my needs.	29	16	45	17	23	40	6	4	10	1	0	1	3.34	SA
													3.46	SA

As shown in Table 6, 60 out of 96 respondents expressed strong confidence in the readiness outcomes, suggesting that the teachers' training is effective in preparing and delivering lessons.

Based on the data derived, nine out of 10 respondents rated the readiness outcomes positively, indicating overwhelming support and validation of the curriculum. The overwhelming agreement among respondents suggested that the learners felt well prepared, consistent with the studies emphasizing the role of structures feedback and teaching effectiveness in fostering readiness for academic and professional challenges (Bradmo & Gamlem, 2025). The high percentage of strong agreement suggests that learners or stakeholders not only acknowledge readiness but also experience it as effective in practice (Saide & Dela Rosa, 2025).

Among the indicators, respondents strongly agreed (weighted mean of 3.34, $f=45$) that the seminars attended by the teachers were applied in the curriculum. Contrary to the above statement, 10 respondents disagreed with this indicator. In other words, the seminars attended by the teachers are relevant and put into practice in their teaching. The data suggested that professional learning is universally designed to connect theory and practice. Based on the data presented above, the transfer of theory varies among teachers. Perceived applicability is important but insufficient for classroom change (OECD, 2023; World Bank, 2020).

With a general weighted mean of 3.46 (Strongly Agree), the findings revealed overwhelmingly positive perceptions of professional development training. The data showed consistent affirmation from the respondents regarding the balance between theory and practice. Respondents also affirmed that seminars are relevant to teaching, feedback mechanisms are effective, and that readiness outcomes are strong.

Table 7. Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum in terms of Resource Availability

RESOURCE AVAILABILITY	SA (4)			A (3)			D (2)			SD (1)			WEIGHTED MEAN	INTERPRETATION
	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL	IS	PS	TOTAL		
Indicators	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f	f		
Teaching materials are tailored and aligned to the Revised K-10 Curriculum	26	23	49	14	16	30	13	4	17	0	0	0	3.33	A
Learning resources are available to teachers.	16	21	37	19	18	37	11	4	15	7	0	7	3.08	A
5. Classrooms are sufficient in terms of the number of students per class.	14	23	37	14	13	27	16	7	23	9	0	9	2.96	A
2. Printed materials like books and modules that are tailored to the Revised K-10 Curriculum are available and sufficient.	9	24	33	15	16	31	19	2	21	10	1	11	2.90	A
3. Technological tools inside the classrooms are available and functional.	12	18	30	12	17	29	17	8	25	12	0	12	2.80	A
													3.01	A

Table 6 presents the Teachers' readiness towards the implementation of the enhanced K-10 Curriculum in terms of Resource Availability in which the printed materials were a weak point, with just a mean of 3.33 ($f=33$) strongly agreed as opposed to ($f=21$) disagreed. In short, roughly two-thirds of the total population saw some level of access or usefulness, but more than one in five teachers report clear shortfalls; an important signal that printed learning materials are a weak point in resource provision. When printed learner materials, teacher guides, or textbooks are missing or insufficient, teachers must improvise or omit planned activities, thereby reducing the likelihood that curriculum intentions are sustained (World Bank, 2022). In addition, shortages of printed materials disproportionately affect remote, multigrade, and low-resource schools; without alternatives, students in those contexts face lower-quality learning opportunities (UNICEF Philippines, 2023).

Technological tools in classrooms and across the school were limited, with a weighted mean of 2.80 ($f=30$), indicating strong agreement; 25 respondents reported disagreement. On one hand, teachers acknowledged the presence of an advanced learning tool. This is very prevalent, especially in Private institutions, based on the data gathered. This situation indicates that some schools are adequately prepared and adept at using technological advancements to aid learning. On the other hand, 25 respondents (out of 96) expressed concerns about the use of technology in classrooms. These results indicated that the Philippines still had a long way to go, underscoring the extent to which equitable ICT resources remained insufficient to implement the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum fully.

With a general weighted mean of 3.01 (Agree), these results highlighted the continuous gaps in printed and technological resources. These results also reflected EDCOM II's identification of uneven resource allocation as a general problem (EDCOM II, 2025). Accessibility to learning resources, printed materials tailored to the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum, and adequate learning spaces remained the weakest domain. With this level of agreement, a consequential gap emerged. Even highly trained teachers cannot fully implement teaching processes without sufficient materials (Abaiz et al, 2025).

Table 9. Comparative analysis in terms of Implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Pedagogical Practices	3.74	Strongly Agree
Impact On Learning	3.56	Strongly Agree
Relevance Of Curriculum	3.38	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	Strongly Agree

The Table 9 shows the measurable indicators, with an overall weighted mean of 3.56 (Strongly Agree) regarding the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum.

With a weighted mean of 3.74 (Strongly Agree), the one that stood out from the rest is the Pedagogical Practices indicator. Based on the results, the respondents believed that the teaching methods used were effective. Teachers also considered that pedagogical quality drives better learning outcomes. Teacher strategies, engagement, and instructional design strongly influence learner performance and views about learning impact.

On the other hand, curriculum relevance ranked last among the indicators with a mean of 3.38 (Strongly Agree). Although it scored lowest, this indicator still received positive feedback from the teachers. This level of agreement among teachers showed a resonance on the quality of the curriculum as essential, well-defined, non-redundant, and most especially relevant to the needs of society.

Table 10. Comparative analysis in terms of Institutional Support Received by the teachers

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Professional Development Training	3.46	Strongly Agree
Received Administrative Support	3.24	Agree
Resource Availability	3.01	Agree
Overall Weighted Mean	3.24	Agree

Based on Table 10, Professional Development Training received the strongest support with a weighted mean of 3.46 (Strongly Agree). The result pronounced that teacher capacity is a relative strength in the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum. Teachers believed that professional development was generally positive and essential, and that it was prioritized during the curriculum roll outs. Although responses were positive, this pattern suggests that teachers can adapt to changes, but it still requires administrative support systems.

Meanwhile, having a weighted mean of 3.01 (Agree), resource availability had the lowest scores. The results indicated tangible gaps in learning materials, facilities, and ICT that limited the implementation of the curriculum. Without adequate materials, labs, and ICT rooms, even well-trained teachers struggled to implement competency-based, contextually relevant curricula effectively. Therefore, addressing resource availability is central to improving curriculum relevance and learning impact.

Table 11. Chi-Squared analysis on Administrative Support

Type of School	4		3		2		1		Total	χ^2	p-value
	<i>f_o</i>	<i>f_e</i>	<i>f_o</i>	<i>f_e</i>	<i>f_o</i>	<i>f_e</i>	<i>f_o</i>	<i>f_e</i>			
Integrated School	123	120.7	77	94.8	51	40.23	13	8.27	264	8.95	
Private School	96	98.29	95	77.2	22	32.77	2	6.73	215	10.4	
Total	219		172		73		15		479	19.35	0.0007
0.05 level of significance										df= (a-1) (r-1)	

To test the hypothesis:

(*df*): degrees of freedom

p-value: $p > \alpha$ (e.g., 0.05): Fail to reject H_0

p-value: $p \leq \alpha$: reject H_0

As shown in the Table 11, the results indicate a significant difference in the level of agreement on readiness for administrative support between teachers of Integrated and Private Schools. the Chi-Squared test result was statistically significant; with $\chi^2(4) = 19.45$, p-value of 0.0007. Since the p-value is less than the level of significance ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis of this study is rejected.

Table 12. Chi- Squared analysis on Professional Development Training

Type of School	4		3		2		1		Total	x ²	p-value
	fo	fe	fo	fe	fo	fe	fo	fe			
Integrated School	168	147.16	72	90.94	23	24.8	1	1.1	264	7.03	
Private School	99	119.84	93	74.06	22	20.2	1	0.9	215	8.63	
Total	267		165		45		2		479	15.66	0.0035

0.05 level of significance

df= (α-1) (r-1)

As shown in Table 12, the difference between teachers in Integrated and Private schools in the level of agreement regarding readiness, grouped by Professional Development Training, yielded an $\chi^2(4) = 15.66$, with a p-value of 0.0035. The data showed a significant difference between teachers in the Integrated and Private schools in the level of agreement regarding readiness, and they were grouped accordingly for Professional Development Training. This was supported by a p-value less than the significance level, so the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 13. Chi- Squared analysis on Resource Availability

Type of School	4		3		2		1		Total	x ²	p-value
	fo	fe	fo	fe	fo	fe	fo	fe			
Integrated School	77	102.51	74	84.88	76	55.67	37	20.94	264	27.48	
Private School	109	83.49	80	69.12	25	45.33	1	17.06	215	33.74	
Total	186		154		101		38		479	61.22	0.0001

0.05 level of significance

df= (a-1) (r-1)

As shown in Table 13, the difference between the two groups is significant, as indicated by the computed Chi-Squared test, $\chi^2(4) = 61.22$. The data showed a significant difference between teachers in Integrated and Private schools in their level of agreement regarding Resource Availability. This was supported by a p-value of 0.0001, which is below the 0.05 significance level ($p < 0.05$); hence, the hypothesis was rejected. This further indicated a significant difference between the two independent groups in this study.

Across all three dimensions, the Chi-Squared test results showed a statistically significant difference between teachers from the Integrated and Private Schools. Based on these data, the Integrated and Private schools do not share the same level of agreement on administrative support, professional development training, and resource allocation. These findings highlighted systemic inequalities between Integrated and Private schools.

Moreover, based on the results presented above, teacher readiness is not only about teachers' competence, institutional support, training opportunities, and resource availability, but also plays a vital role in fully realizing the goals and objectives of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum.

Chapter 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

After all responses were collected, analyzed, and interpreted, and conclusions were drawn, this chapter presented the findings of the study. It also formulated recommended actions and developmental plans based on the results. These findings may serve as references for the identified stakeholders and significant members of the community.

To answer Research Question 1, teachers from both Integrated and Private Schools strongly agreed that the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum embodied essential skills appropriate to learners' developmental levels, aligned with global demands, and remained relevant to local needs. These findings were based on a general weighted mean of 3.38. This high level of agreement regarding

curriculum relevance suggested that teachers perceived the curriculum as conceptually sound and aligned with both global standards and local contexts. It also indicated sustained prioritization of maintaining clarity of objectives and eliminating redundant competencies.

A similarly high level of agreement was reflected in the perceived impact of the curriculum on learning. The indicator assessed whether the curriculum strengthened foundational literacy and numeracy skills and developed critical thinking abilities. Teachers' strong agreement, reflected in a general weighted mean of 3.56, suggested high expectations that the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum would enhance both foundational competencies and higher-order thinking skills.

Overall, the results for the first core indicator highlighted that curriculum reforms must sustain active learning approaches; however, successful implementation depends on teachers possessing adequate pedagogical competencies. The combined indicators affirmed that teachers in both Integrated and Private Schools demonstrated comparable levels of agreement regarding readiness for curriculum implementation.

To answer Research Question 2 regarding administrative support, teachers rated the training received as available, relevant, and generally sufficient. Nevertheless, variability in perceived sufficiency indicated areas for improvement. Access to learning resources, printed materials aligned with the new curriculum, appropriate classroom-to-student ratios, and technological resources remained the weakest areas. The dispersion of responses suggested uneven material readiness across schools. Without sufficient instructional materials and resources, even highly trained and experienced teachers may encounter difficulties in implementing the curriculum effectively.

To answer Research Question 3, the results of the Chi-Square Test for Homogeneity revealed statistically significant differences in the level of agreement regarding readiness across three dimensions: (a) administrative support ($p = 0.0007$), (b) professional development training ($p = 0.0035$), and (c) resource availability ($p = 0.0001$).

These results highlighted disparities that influenced teachers' perceptions and preparedness within their respective educational contexts. Taken together, the findings emphasized that readiness was not solely a matter of teacher competence but was also influenced by administrative and institutional support.

The consistent rejection of the null hypothesis across all dimensions confirmed that Integrated and Private Schools operated under distinct conditions that shaped teachers' readiness. Policymakers and school leaders must recognize these disparities and prioritize interventions that promote equity in administrative support, professional development, and resource allocation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Teachers from both Integrated and Private Schools were theoretically and practically ready to implement the Enhanced K–10 Curriculum. However, systemic challenges related to resources and administrative support continued to burden teachers.
2. Clear communication regarding curriculum reforms should be maintained to reduce confusion and ambiguity. When teachers perceived the curriculum as relevant, they were more likely to invest time and effort in planning, adjusting, and sustaining new pedagogical approaches.
3. To minimize ambiguity in disseminating curriculum reforms, a clear and structured implementation process is necessary. Addressing teachers' concerns is essential to ensure that educators—regardless of school type—are adequately prepared to adapt to reforms and deliver quality education.

4. To address learning gaps, equity in resource allocation is critical. Without sufficient instructional materials and infrastructure (e.g., classrooms, science laboratories, and computer laboratories), teachers cannot fully implement the intended pedagogical approaches.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for the Division of San Carlos City and Diocesan Schools to better equip teachers as front liners in curriculum implementation:

Department of Education. Given the significant differences between Integrated and Private Schools, it is recommended that comprehensive, timely, and realistic curricular reform policies be developed. Equitable resource allocation across provinces should be ensured. Revisiting the Instructional Design Framework (IDF) and aligning it with the MATATAG Curriculum is also recommended to remove redundancies and enhance essential competencies.

Schools Division and Diocesan Superintendents. Sustainable recapacitating programs should be implemented for both experienced and newly hired teachers. These initiatives will allow educators to deepen their understanding of curricular changes and clarify policy ambiguities.

School Heads. Professional development initiatives should prioritize practical classroom strategies rather than theoretical discussions alone. Refresher workshops and seminars may be reinforced through Focused Group Discussions (FGDs) and School Learning Action Cells (SLACs). Prompt attention to teacher and learner concerns should remain a priority.

Stakeholders. Recognizing that education is a shared responsibility, stronger collaboration among schools, communities, and the Local Government Unit is recommended. Enhanced partnerships can improve the acquisition, distribution, and utilization of instructional materials and resources, thereby helping to reduce learning gaps, particularly in remote areas.

Proposed Development Plan

SCHOOL-BASED PROFESSIONAL LEARNING COMMUNITY (PLC):

Recapacitating the Integrated and Private Junior High School Teachers

Locale: **Division of San Carlos City**

Target Group: **Integrated and Private Junior High Schools**

Timeline: **School year 2026-2027**

Rationale:

Teachers are known as the front liners in the curriculum implementation. To equip them with the essential knowledge, skills, and pedagogies, it is essential for them to materialize the desired outcomes stated the curricular guides and to improve learning outcomes. With this, the program is established to recapacitate our teachers for them to be ready in the implementation of the Enhanced K-10 curriculum for the school year 2026-2027.

Program objectives:

1. Recapacitate teachers in terms of theoretical and pedagogical strategies in teaching the Enhanced K-10 curriculum.
2. Sustain high level of teacher readiness in terms of curricular relevance, pedagogies, and professional development.
3. complete the 32 hours requirement on Professional Development per school year.

Program	Objective	Core activities	Person/s in charge	Timeframe	Expected output	Source of Funds
1. Orientation & Curriculum Mapping	Align teachers to Enhanced K–10 scope and priorities	Teaching staff orientation; grade-level mapping workshops	School Head/ Master Teacher	Opening Block of School Year 2026-2027 (5 days at most) June 8-11, 2026	Refined, clear objectives and competencies in every learning area in curriculum maps	School MOOE; School operating budget
2. PLC Establishment and Coaching	Subject-specific pedagogy for priority learning areas Create grade-level coaching cycles	Classroom Observations, Workshops; demo lessons; remedial planning	School Head, Master Teacher School Head, Master Teacher, External Persons (who are experts on the area)	(5 days) Enrichment Block of Trimester 1st Trimester September 2-15, 2026	Enhanced teaching pedagogies through Lesson plans (LPs) especially to the newly hired teachers	School MOOE; School operating budget
	Build diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment practices Create and established refined Table of Specifications (TOS) per grade level	SLAC workshops; item-writing; classroom trials		2nd Trimester December 7-18, 2026 3rd Trimester March 24-April 8, 2027	Enriched Table of Specifications per grade level aligned to the competencies Drafts on summative examinations per grade level for the next trimester	
3. Monitoring, Data Use & Reporting	Use learner data to refine and establish best practices per grade level instruction Prepare for external validation and continuous improvement Create Annual Review and Systemic updating from Curriculum Implementation Division (CID)	School PIRPA, Analysis on MEAN Percentage Scores of learners in every Subject Area	School Head, Master Teacher Education Program Supervisors (EPS) Public Schools Division Supervisors	At the end of every Enrichment Block Period After School PIRPA	Comparative analysis on ACTUAL Mean Percentage Scores (MPS) of learners in every Trimester.	School MOOE; School operating budget

PROPOSED PROGRAM MATRIX

Strengthening Readiness and Equity in the Implementation of the Enhanced K-10 Curriculum in Junior High Schools in the Division of San Carlos City

Locale: Division of San Carlos City

Target Group: Integrated and Private Junior High Schools

Timeline: School year 2026-2027

Rationale:

Curriculum design and teacher pedagogy are not the primary constraints in the implementation of the curriculum. operational and access to resources remained an obstacle. With this the program is proposed to aid and mitigate the planning stage of equitable resources.

Objective:

1. Address insufficiencies in learning resources, technological tools, and classroom facilities.

Areas of Concern:

1. Resource availability (books, modules, technology, classroom sufficiency)
2. Administrative responsiveness

Persons Involved:

1. School Heads from Integrated and Private Schools
2. LGU Representatives
3. Division Office
4. Private School Associations
5. Teachers
6. Parent- Teacher Association Representatives

Strategic Priority	Key Activity	Estimated Cost (PHP)	Timeline	Primary Funding Source
Resource Audit and Mapping	Division-wide audit of textbooks, modules, ICT, classroom capacity.	₱300,000	0–2 months	Division budget; minimal LGU support
Emergency Provisioning	Emergency kits: textbooks, teacher guides, basic ICT bundles for priority schools.	₱2,400,000	1–3 months	Division contingency; LGU; PTA; donor in-kind
Administrative Standardization	Develop and print Division Implementation Manual; digital distribution.	₱120,000	0–3 months	Division admin budget
ICT Rollout and Pedagogical	Procure projectors, shared tablets, offline resources, teacher ICT	₱3,500,000 phased 6–18 months	6–18 months	Division capital; LGU; private partners

Integration	training.			
Classroom Reconfiguration and Infrastructure	Minor renovations, furniture, phased classroom upgrades.	₱4,000,000 phased 6–24 months	6–24 months	LGU capital; Division matching funds

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